

Solubilising Action of Different Basic Organic Compounds on Metallic Soaps

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The view that any compound, which is structurally both a glycol and an amine, preferably a secondary amine like diethanolamine, may play a far more powerful role in solubilising metallic soaps has been experimentally corroborated in case of zinc, barium, and lithium laurates. Further, the joint action of an amine or alkylolamine plus a glycol has been investigated in the expectation that the combination may be more potent than individual additives in all dissolution processes. The results are in fair agreement with this theoretical expectation.

It has been shown by Chatterjee and Palit¹ that organic bases like diethanolamine, triethanolamine, and piperidine are very powerful solubilisers for metallic soaps of lead and zinc (laurates and stearates) as compared with ordinary glycols or amines.

The present paper describes the experiments and results of an extension of the same work with other soaps like laurates of Zn, Ba, and Li and stearates of Zn and Pb in order to elucidate further the mechanism of this solubilising action of different bases and their suitable mixtures in chloroform.

EXPERIMENTAL

Merck's pure stearic acid after crystallisation three times from hot ethanol was used, m.p. 69-70°. Lauric acid from the Eastman Kodak pure analytical sample (previous sample was obtained from Pisa seeds²) was taken and purified by crystallisation from hot ethanol, m.p. 43-44°. The corresponding metal soaps were prepared by interaction of the metallic salt solution in a small quantity of distilled water (taking approx. 4% in excess of the theoretical amount) and a hot ethanolic solution of sodium soap, the latter being added dropwise while the whole medium was continuously stirred, preferably at 40° to 50°. The precipitate was filtered on a Buchner funnel and repeatedly washed with hot distilled water until the filtrate gave negative test for the metal salt used. The samples, thus prepared, were dried, crystallised from hot chloroform solution, and analysed quantitatively by standard methods. In case of Li-soap, the chloride was prepared by decomposing the calculated amount of carbonate by 1*N*-HCl. The percentages of respective metal contents are: zinc stearate, 10.25% Zn (calc. 10.36%); zinc laurate, 14.12% Zn

1. Chatterjee and Palit, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 421.

2. Puntambekar and Krishna, *ibid.*, 1953, 10, 395; Agarwal, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1950, 9B, 275.

(calc. 14.09%); lead stearate, 26.70% Pb (calc. 26.78%); lead laurate, 34.17% Pb (calc., 34.21%); barium laurate, 26.20% Ba (calc. 25.60); lithium laurate, 3.71% Li (calc. 3.51%).

The soap was taken in a pyrex tube (18 × 70mm) fitted with a ground glass stop-cock, the solvent was quickly introduced, and weighed. The tube was kept suspended ~~up~~ to the neck inside water in a glass bath heated to a regulated temperature (controlled within $\pm 0.5^\circ$) and the corresponding "solution temperature" (S.T.) was observed carefully. The solution was maintained each time at the corresponding S. T. for a considerable period to verify that complete solution had not taken place. Additives (or mixtures of additives) in measured drops were introduced through a fine syringe and corresponding readings for S. T. were noted. In case of co-solvency experiment, a saturated solution was prepared by shaking the soap in requisite proportion of additives in chloroform with the help of a mechanical shaker; the soap solution was suspended in a thermostat at 35° overnight. After equilibrium the solution was filtered quickly at 35° and solubilities were measured by evaporating the solvent, washing the soap with water to free it of glycols or amines, and finally weighing directly in a tared Gooch crucible.

Zinc Soaps

Zinc Laurate.— Figs. 1, 2, 3, and 4 represent the observations of 1.75% by weight of the soap in CHCl_3 with different additives, both taken singly and also in a suitable mixture. Fig. 1 shows the solubilising action of triethanolamine—propylene glycol mixture as additive on 1.75% soap in CHCl_3 . It appears that a 80:20 mole ratio mixture of triethanolamine—propylene glycol is the most active. The solubilising action of the same glycol in combination with different amines, e.g., piperidine, diethylamine, and diethanolamine, is respectively shown in Figs. 2, 3, and 4. In all these cases it is observed that a suitable combination of the glycol and the amine is the most active solubiliser.

Wt.% additive.
FIG. 1. TEA: P.G.

Curve A	0 : 100	Curve D	100 : 0
B	85 : 15	E	90 : 10
C	75 : 25	F	80 : 20

Wt.% additive.

FIG. 2. Piperidine : P.G.

Curve A	0 : 100	Curve D	98 : 2
B	100 : 0	E	95 : 5
C	99.5 : 0.5	F	96 : 4
		G	99 : 1

as only 46°. Fig. 6 shows the effect of diethanolamine on the solution temperature of different amounts of zinc stearate in CHCl_3 where as high as 10.5% by weight of soap can be solubilised by 7.0% additive (DEA) at 30°. Fig. 7 represents the co-solubility curves of zinc stearate with the additive (propyleneglycol+diethanolamine) in a fixed mole fraction of chloroform.

The observed fact that a 10 mole additive (diethanolamine: propyleneglycol=90:10) in 90 moles CHCl_3 can effectively solubilise 12.0% by weight of soap at 35° is of great importance in view of the insoluble nature of the stearate.

FIG. 6. Effect of DEA on S.T. in CHCl_3 soln.
Curves A—D represent respectively
10.5, 7.0, 3.5 and 1.75% soap.

Mole prop. of amine in the additive.
FIG. 7.

A = 10% mixture (DEA : PG). B = 10%
mixture (TEA : PG). C = 5% mixture
(DEA : PG). D = 5% mixture (TEA : PG).
E = 3% mixture (TEA : PG).

B. Lead Soaps

Lead Laurate.—In our previous communications, we studied 2% by volume, i.e. 1.33% by weight, of soap in chloroform with additives like mono-, di-, tri-ethanolamines, piperidine, pyridine, mono-, di-, tri-ethylamines, etc. Diethanolamine was found to be the most effective so far the individual case was concerned. Fig. 8 represents the observations with 1.72% by weight of lead laurate in chloroform with different mole proportions

of additives like diethanolamine—propylene glycol and triethanolamine—propylene glycol. In conformity with our viewpoint, we find the additive having 90:10 mole. ratio mixture of diethanolamine: propylene glycol to be the most powerful.

Lead Stearate.—In the case of 1.33% by weight of lead soap in chloroform, piperidine seems to be the most effective, followed by morpholine, the amount of additive being less than 1%. The comparative effects of different secondary amines (as also alkylamine) on solution temperature of 1% by weight of lead stearate in chloroform were studied. The results are shown in Fig. 9. The peculiar observation is the superior effect of comparatively weak bases like dibutylamine, or diethylamine and the inferior action of the usually expected strong base, diethanolamine.

Wt. % additive.
FIG. 8

A—PG. B. TEA : PG=95 : 5. C. TEA : PG=97 : 3. D. DEA : PG=97 : 3. E. TEA. F. TEA : PG=90 : 10. G. DEA : PG=95 : 5. H. DEA. I. DEA : PG=90 : 10 (in moles).

Wt. % additive.
FIG. 9

A—Diphenylamine.
B—DEA.
C—Diethylamine.
D—Dibutylamine.

Barium Soap

Barium Laurate.—Barium soap (1% by wt.) was studied with additives like piperidine, mono-, di-, and tri-ethanolamines and diethylamine. Diethanolamine is found to be the most powerful, followed by triethanolamine, diethylamine, monoethanolamine and last piperidine in the series. The results are shown in Fig. 10.

The effect of the mixture was studied in two cases. In the case of mixture of diethanolamine and propylene glycol, the effect is not very prominent; for a short range of concentra-

tion it works as a superior agent, but at lower ranges of temperature (i.e. at higher concentration) the effect is not at all pronounced. Again, unlike this mixture, the other, i.e., triethanolamine: propylene glycol, works more satisfactorily under identical conditions.

FIG. 10

A—DEA. B—DEA : PG=80 : 20 in CHCl_3 . C—PG. D—TEA : PG=80 : 20 in CHCl_3 . E—TEA. F—diethylamine. G—monoethanolamine. H—pyridine. I—piperidine

D. Lithium Soap

Lithium Laurate.—Similar is the observation with lithium soap. Fig. 11 records the observations where 1% by weight of soap is shown to be fairly soluble at room temperature in presence of 4.0% additive like triethanolamine. Again, the most interesting feature is the observation of the joint action of triethanolamine and propylene glycol / ethylene glycol, where 4.0% by weight of soap becomes easily solubilised below 50° by the addition of a 10% mixture in mole proportion of 75 : 25.

Fig. 12 represents the co-solubility curve of lithium laurate with the additive (propylene glycol + triethanolamine) in a fixed mole fraction of CHCl_3 . The soap (2% by weight) was dissolved at 35° by 10 moles of additive in 90 moles of chloroform, the composition of additive being in the ratio of triethanolamine: propylene glycol=60:40 moles.

DISCUSSION

From the foregoing studies it follows that among the members of a particular series like mono-, di-, and tri-ethanolamines, the secondary base is found to be the most active

due to the larger availability of its lone-pair electrons as discussed by Palit³, the comparative effectiveness following in the order: DEA > TEA > monoethanolamine.

Wt. % additive.
 FIG. 11. A—TEA : PG=75 : 25 moles.
 B— „ : EG=75 : 25
 C—PG. D—DEA. E—TEA.

TEMP. 35°C
 FIG. 12.
 A—90 moles CHCl_3 : 10 moles additive.
 B—95 „ CHCl_3 : 5 „ additive.

Since secondary amines are powerful solubilisers for metal soaps and glycols are fairly strong co-solvents, our view, that the joint action of such an amine and a glycol may play a far more powerful role in solubilising metallic soaps, is fairly corroborated from these experiments (vide Figs. 1 to 4).

The list shown in Table I also confirms the above viewpoint and records a gradation of additives and their suitable mixtures on a comparative scale, indicating their power of dissolution of zinc soaps (stearate) within an approximate range of 30-35°.

It is evident that the effectiveness in terms of solubilising power may be viewed in two ways. In one case, we find a steep fall in the run of S.T. curves but not to a very low range of temperature, i.e., with a few drops of additive the initial drop in solution temperature is very marked, but after that the course of the run cannot be followed due to residual haziness indicating insolubility. This is observed in case of many secondary amines, like piperidine, morpholine, etc. (vide curve B of Fig. 2).

In the other case, the continuity in dropping solution temperature can be smoothly maintained without any break or haziness though the steepness is not so sharp as in the former. In such cases, the observation can be recorded down to as low a temperature

as the melting point of ice without any discontinuity. This is observed in the case of secondary alkylolamines, particularly in diethanolamine, as represented in curve D of Fig. 6. Both these types of behaviour can be viewed as good criteria of effective solubilisers.

TABLE I

Solubilising power of various additives in chloroform on different amount of zinc stearate.

Amount of additive.	Amount of zinc stearate solubilised.	Solubilising temperature.
Ca: 5.0% PG	1.33 %	> 35°
Ca: 5.0% Morpholine	1.33	> 35°
Ca: 5.0% Pyridine	1.33	> 35°
0.76% DEA	1.75	30°
1.86% DEA	3.5	30°
4.3% DEA	7.0	30°
10% Mixture (TEA : PG = 4:1)	10.4	35°
10% Mixture (DEA : PG = 1:1)	12.0	35°

N.B. DEA, TEA and PG denote respectively di- and tri- ethanolamine and propylene glycol.

FIG. 13. Variations of S.T. of metallic laurates in CHCl_3 with diff. additives.

A=1.0% Ba $\text{L}t_2$ in DEA. B=1.33% Pb $\text{L}t_2$ in DEA. C=1.75% Zn $\text{L}t_2$ in DEA.
 D=1.0% Ba $\text{L}t_2$ in TEA. E=1.33% Pb $\text{L}t_2$ in TEA. F=1.75% Zn $\text{L}t_2$ in TEA.
 G=1.0% Ba $\text{L}t_2$ in PG. H=1.0% Li $\text{L}t$ in PG. I=1.33 Pb $\text{L}t_2$ in PG.
 J=1.0 Li $\text{L}t_2$ in TEA K=1.75% Zn $\text{L}t_2$ in PG.

It is of interest to study comparatively the solution temperature values against the corresponding mole ratio of additives and soaps as in Fig. 13. This figure clearly shows the wide variance of these values in case of different soaps. It is quite likely that there is loose type of complex formation between the peptising agent and the soap involved, but the present data do not lead to an unequivocal value for the stoichiometric composition of the complex, if any.

On the basis of the existing knowledge that amines form co-ordinate complexes with many central metal atoms and also from the mechanism of solubilising action of glycols on soaps, as suggested by Palit^{3,4,7} we may well imagine that highly insoluble lithium soaps are brought into solution by simultaneous solvation of the metal atom by nitrogen through a co-ordinate bond and the carboxylate oxygen atom through hydrogen-bond formation with the glycolic hydroxyl groups. A rough picture of this simultaneous solvation is shown by structures (I) and (II).

With polyvalent metals like zinc and lead, two or even more moles of amine may be involved as represented in structure (III) because of their increased accommodating power for the lone pairs of electrons of the basic nitrogen atoms in the amino type of peptisers⁵.

4. Palit and McBain, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1946, 38, 741.

5. Pink and Tughan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1804.

In conclusion, it is interesting to remark that in accordance with a parallel idea due to Winsor⁶ in his affinity ratio 'R', we can easily think that in case of co-solvency of metallic soaps, the ultimate principle is more or less similar to the view expressed by him that there must exist a balanced attraction between the various active parts present in the co-dissolving agents and the corresponding polar/non-polar portion of the soap molecule.

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7. Palit, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 3120.